

Synthesis and Pharmacology of some New Methyl 4-[2-Alkylthio-4(3*H*)-quinazolon-3-yl]phenyl Acetates†

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Some methyl 4-[2-alkylthio-4(3*H*)-quinazolon-3-yl]phenyl acetates and phenyl- α -methyl acetates (4-7, Table 1) have been synthesised and evaluated for their pharmacological activities. Some of the compounds showed moderate antiinflammatory activity.

VARIOUS biological activities¹, such as antiarthritic, anticonvulsant, hypnotic, analgesic *etc.* have been associated with quinazolinone molecule. Prior publications²⁻⁵ from these laboratories described the synthesis and antiinflammatory activity of a variety of 4-heteroarylphenylalkanoic acid derivatives. In a continued search for new compounds possessing antiinflammatory and antiarthritic activities the synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of some methyl 4-[2-alkylthio-4(3*H*)-quinazolon-3-yl]phenyl acetates and phenyl- α -methyl acetates (5) have been carried out. Furthermore, the ability to inhibit the prostaglandin synthesis has been viewed as a basic mode of antiinflammatory action of the non-steroidal antiinflammatory agents (NSAI). In view of this, some title compounds (6 and 7) carrying the side-chain moiety analogous to that of prostaglandins have also been synthesised and evaluated for their antiinflammatory and blood platelet aggregation inhibiting activities.

Methyl 4-isothiocyanato-phenyl acetates (2a, b) were prepared in excellent yields by reaction of the corresponding 4-aminophenyl acetates (1a, b) in acetone with thiophosgene. Treatment of 2a, b with anthranilic acid in boiling ethanol following the method of Dave *et al.*⁶ furnished the corresponding 2-mercaptoquinazolones (3a, b) in very good yields. Ir spectra of 3 showed bands around 3250 (NH), 1665 (ketonic C=O) and 1720 cm⁻¹ (ester C=O). Alkylation of 3 with appropriate alkyl halide in boiling acetone in presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ gave the title compounds (4-6) in fairly good yields. Reduction of the 2-oxo-heptylthio analogues (6a and 6b) using aluminium isopropoxide gave the corresponding hydroxy derivatives (7a, b) in very good yield.

The structures of all the compounds reported in Table 1 are based on their correct elemental analyses

and supported by their ir and pmr spectra of representative compounds (Experimental).

Pharmacology: All the compounds reported in Table 1 were screened for their various pharmacological activities following the standard methods⁷. Approximate LD₅₀ (ALD₅₀), gross observational effects, reduction in spontaneous and forced locomotor activity and pentobarbitone hypnosis potentiation were studied in albino mice of Swiss strain, while effects on conditioned avoidance response (CAR) and electro-shock seizures were tested in Wistar strain albino rats. The antiinflammatory activity was evaluated by carrageenin-induced rat paw-oedema method at 0.2 of ALD₅₀/kg (p.o.) dose as described by Winter *et al.*⁸, and the results are included in Table 1. Prostaglandin E, has been reported to possess marked blood platelet aggregation inhibiting activity⁹. Keeping in view of the structural resemblances of the side chain moiety present in compounds 6a, 6b, 7a and 7b to that of prostaglandin side chain, these four compounds were also tested for adenosine-phosphate (ADP) induced blood-platelet aggregation inhibiting activity *in vitro* in rat's platelet rich plasma following the turbidimetric method of Born and Cross¹⁰.

Several 2-alkylthioquinazolonyl derivatives reported herein as well as the parent 2-mercapto derivatives 3 exhibited moderate antiinflammatory activity. Thus, compounds 3a, b; 4a, c, d, e; 5b-e; and 6a were found to possess moderate activity of 4.3-34.28% inhibition of oedema. Compounds 4c and 5e exhibited highest antiinflammatory activity of 34.28 and 30.11% inhibition respectively as compared to 48% by phenylbutazone at 85 mg/kg (p.o.) dose. In addition to this, four compounds (3a, 4c, 5a and 5c) displayed mild CNS depressant activity by showing reduction on spontaneous locomotor activity, reduced body and limb tone

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TABLE 1—METHYL-4-[(2-ALKYLTHIO-4(3H)-QUINAZOLON-3-YL)PHENYL]ACETATES*

Compd. no.	R ₁	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis N% : Found/(Calcd.)	Antiinflammatory** activity % Inhibition
3a	H	220	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.27 (8.59)	4.3
3b	H	235	90	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.51 (8.23)	18.0
4a	CH ₃	122	94	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.13 (8.23)	4.3
4b	C ₂ H ₅	102	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.91 (7.91)	N.A.
4c	n-C ₃ H ₇	85	55	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.86 (7.61)	34.28
4d	n-C ₄ H ₉	80	66	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.09 (7.33)	17.69
4e	CH ₃ ,C ₆ H ₅	105	65	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	6.57 (6.73)	29.61
5a	CH ₃	165	90	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.98 (7.91)	N.A.
5b	C ₂ H ₅	132	78	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.78 (7.59)	15.42
5c	n-C ₃ H ₇	97	70	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.48 (7.33)	25.57
5d	n-C ₄ H ₉	90	71	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	6.91 (7.07)	11.93
5e	CH ₃ ,C ₆ H ₅	118	70	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	6.70 (6.51)	30.11
6a	CH ₃ ,CO,C ₆ H ₁₁	115	35	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄ S	6.05 (6.39)	20.93
6b	CH ₃ ,CO,C ₆ H ₁₁	142	55	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₄ S	6.32 (6.19)	N.A.
7a	CH ₃ ,OH,OH,C ₆ H ₁₁	97	91	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₄ S	6.54 (6.36)	N.A.
7b	CH ₃ ,OH,OH,C ₆ H ₁₁	128	70	C ₂₆ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₄ S	6.60 (6.16)	11.0

* Satisfactory C and H analyses obtained.

** Approximate LD₅₀ (ALD₅₀) in mice of all compounds is more than 1000 mg/kg (p.o.) except compound 4b (792 mg/kg, i.p.); N.A.=not active.

Scheme 1

and ataxia. None of the compounds tested showed any inhibition of blood platelet aggregation in rat's plasma at 0.001 M concentration.

Experimental

The general methods for the synthesis of the typical compounds are described below.

Methyl 4-isothiocyanatophenyl acetate (2a): A solution of thiophosgene (28.50 g, 0.25 mol) in acetone (50 ml), was added dropwise to a stirred mixture of methyl-4-aminophenylacetate (1a; 41.25 g, 0.25 mol) and sodium bicarbonate (42.0 g, 0.5 mol) in acetone (150 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for further 1 h at room temperature. It was poured over crushed ice, then the resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from hot ethanol to yield the pure title compound (41.5 g, 80%), m.p. 168-70° (Found: C, 58.00; H, 4.54; N, 6.82. C₁₀H₉NO₂S requires C, 57.97; H, 4.34; N, 6.76%); ν_{max} (nujol) 2050 (NCS) and 1720 cm⁻¹ (ester C=O).

Methyl 4-isothiocyanatophenyl-α-methyl acetate (2b): Following the previous procedure, it was obtained by the reaction of methyl 4-aminophenyl-α-methyl acetate with thiophosgene, as thick syrupy

liquid (88%) (Found : C, 60.00 ; H, 5.02 ; N, 6.52. $C_{11}H_{11}NO_2S$ requires C, 59.73 ; H, 4.97 ; N, 6.33%) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 2100 (NCS) and 1735 cm^{-1} (ester C=O).

Methyl 4-[2-mercapto-4(3H)-quinazolon-3-yl]phenyl- α -methyl acetate (3b) : A mixture of **2b** (22.1 g, 0.1 mol) and anthranilic acid (13.7 g, 0.1 mol) in absolute ethanol (200 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The solid separated out on cooling was filtered, washed with 10% aqueous NaHCO_3 solution followed by water. It was recrystallised from hot ethanol to yield pure **3b** (30.6 g, 90%), m.p. $233-35^\circ$ (Found : C, 63.63 ; H, 5.00 ; N, 8.51. $C_{18}H_{16}N_2O_3S$ requires C, 63.53 ; H, 4.70 ; N, 8.23%) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 3220 (NH) , 1720 (ester C=O) and 1650 cm^{-1} (ketonic C=O) ; δ ($\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{TFA}$) 1.70 (3H, d, $\alpha\text{-CH}_3$), 3.90 (3H, s, COOCH_3), 3.9-4.1 (1H, m, $\alpha\text{-H}$) and 7.3-8.5 (8H, m, ArH).

3a (Table 1) was similarly prepared.

Methyl 4-[2-methylthio-4(3H)quinazolon-3-yl]phenyl acetate (4a) : A mixture of **3a** (3.26 g, 0.01 mol), freshly fused K_2CO_3 (2.76 g, 0.02 mol) and methyl iodide (2.84 g, 0.02 mol) in dry acetone (100 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was filtered, K_2CO_3 was washed with hot acetone (25 ml) and the combined acetone filtrate was concentrated to dryness. The residue was column chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with chloroform gave the title compound which was recrystallised from hot ethanol to give pure **4a** (3.2 g, 94%), m.p. $120-22^\circ$ (Found : C, 63.50 ; H, 4.82 ; N, 8.13. $C_{18}H_{16}N_2O_3S$ requires C, 63.53 ; H, 4.70 ; N, 8.23%) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 1720 (ester C=O) and 1690 cm^{-1} (ketonic C=O) ; PMR δ (CDCl_3) 2.60 (3H, s, S-CH_3), 3.80 (5H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{COOCH}_3$) and 7.3-8.50 (8H, m, ArH).

4b-e, **5a-e** and **6a, b** were prepared in a similar manner by reaction of the corresponding **3** with appropriate alkyl halide.

Methyl 4-[2-(2-hydroxyheptylthio)-4(3H)quinazolin-3-yl]phenyl acetate (7a) : A mixture of **6a** (0.438 g, 0.001 mol) and aluminium isopropoxide (0.204 g, 0.001 mol) in isopropanol (50 ml) was very slowly (5-10 drops/min) distilled on a water-bath till

the elimination of acetone was completed (2,4-DNP test). The excess of isopropanol was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was hydrolysed with 10% dilute HCl (25 ml). It was extracted with ether and ether extract was washed with H_2O and dried (Na_2SO_4). After removing the solvent, the residue was filtered through a small alumina column and eluted with CHCl_3 . The compound obtained from CHCl_3 eluent was recrystallised from ether-hexane to yield the pure title compound (0.4 g, 91%), m.p. 97° (Found : C, 65.66 ; H, 6.40 ; N, 6.54. $C_{24}H_{28}N_2O_4S$ requires C, 65.45 ; H, 6.36 ; N, 6.36%) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 3320 (OH), 1730 (ester C=O) and 1690 cm^{-1} (C=O).

7b was similarly prepared in 70% yield by reaction of **6b** with aluminium isopropoxide, (70%) m.p. 128° (Found : C, 66.31 ; H, 6.66 ; N, 6.60. $C_{25}H_{30}N_2O_4S$ requires C, 66.07 ; H, 6.60 ; N, 6.16%) ; ν_{max} (nujol) 3420 (OH), 1730 (ester C=O) and 1690 cm^{-1} (C=O).

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